

Implementing Careless Whisper: Tracking Phone Presence States via Signal’s Silent Delivery Receipts

An Empirical Reproduction Study

Advait Amit Desai Harshal Ajit Kamble Soham Sunil Margaj

Dept. of Information Technology, Veermata Jijabai Technological Institute (VJTI), Mumbai 400 019, India

{aadesai_b23, kakamble_b23, ssmargaj_b23}@it.vjti.ac.in

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Abstract. We present a reproduction of the *Careless Whisper* attack introduced by Gegenhuber et al. [1] (RAID 2025, Best Paper Award), applied to Signal Messenger on iOS. The attack exploits a side-channel in Signal’s delivery receipt mechanism: by sending reactions to fabricated message identifiers, an observer can elicit silent delivery receipts from a target device and classify its activity state—app in foreground, screen on, screen off, or offline—from the resulting round-trip time (RTT), without the target receiving any notification. We implemented the *Spooky Stranger* variant using `signal-cli` and Python, and conducted a controlled experiment with an informed and consenting subject over a 30-minute session. We collected 23,623 probe–receipt pairs and verified all four device states against ground truth. Our key empirical observations are: (i) a probe interval of **20 seconds** is necessary to allow the target device to enter deep sleep reliably—shorter intervals keep the OS in a light-sleep state and mask the screen-off condition; (ii) at intervals as low as **0.25 seconds** the attack provides near-continuous presence tracking. Our results corroborate that this is a genuine, exploitable privacy flaw in Signal on iOS.

Note on consent and ethics. All experiments were conducted on the device of Shri Vishakh Devanand (vdshri_b23@e1.vjti.ac.in), who provided explicit informed consent and was aware of the monitoring throughout. This work was conducted solely for academic research as part of a Systems Security laboratory course at VJTI.

1 Introduction

End-to-end encryption protects the *content* of messages on platforms like Signal, but protocol-level *metadata*—who messages whom, and when—can remain exposed. A subtle form of metadata leakage arises from *delivery receipts*: automatic acknowledgements sent by a client whenever a message envelope is successfully decrypted.

Gegenhuber et al. [1] showed that on several major encrypted messaging platforms, delivery receipts are gen-

erated before the client checks whether the referenced content is meaningful. An attacker can send a reaction to a non-existent message ID to a target’s phone number, receive a silent delivery receipt, and measure the round-trip time (RTT). The RTT acts as a proxy for the device’s activity: whether the app is in the foreground, whether the screen is on, whether the phone is in deep sleep, or whether it is offline. No notification appears on the target’s device, and no message is stored.

The original paper evaluated the attack across Signal, WhatsApp, Threema, and others. **Our contribution is not a new attack**; we implement, run, and empirically evaluate the existing attack as described in [1], specifically targeting Signal on iOS, and report a practical observation about probe-interval effects on deep-sleep detection that is not explicitly discussed in the original work.

2 Background

2.1 Silent Delivery Receipts

Signal mandates that a client send a delivery receipt as soon as the sender’s message envelope is decrypted, regardless of content. The flaw identified in [1] is that this receipt is emitted *before* the client validates whether the referenced content exists. A reaction envelope referencing a fictitious message ID still produces a receipt, and because the envelope is end-to-end encrypted, Signal’s servers cannot distinguish it from a legitimate reaction.

2.2 The Spooky Stranger Variant

We implement the *Spooky Stranger* variant: the attacker and target need no prior conversation and the attacker need not be in the target’s contact list. A reaction is addressed to the target’s phone number with a fabricated `targetTimestamp`. Signal delivers it; the device decrypts and discards the reaction (no notification, no stored message) and automatically issues a delivery receipt.

2.3 RTT-to-State Mapping

The RTT reflects the device’s power and network state at the time of delivery (Table 1). A foreground app responds nearly instantly; background delivery requires an OS wake-

up; deep sleep causes the OS to defer push processing, inflating the RTT.

Table 1: RTT threshold mapping from Table IV of [1].

RTT	Inferred State
< 500 ms	App in foreground
500–1,000 ms	Screen on, app background
1,000–2,500 ms	Screen on, idle
> 2,500 ms	Screen off / deep sleep
No receipt (> 30 s)	Device offline

3 Implementation

We implemented the attack in Python 3 using `signal-cli` 0.13 as the Signal protocol client. The system has five components:

- **Prober:** sends a reaction to a fabricated `targetTimestamp` at a configurable interval, recording the send time per probe.
- **Receipt Listener:** consumes incoming envelopes from a `signal-cli` JSON-RPC subprocess, identifies delivery receipts, and matches them to outstanding probes.
- **RTT Calculator:** computes $RTT = t_{receipt} - t_{probe}$ using monotonic timestamps to avoid wall-clock skew.
- **Analyzer:** maps each RTT to a device state (Table 1) with a 20-probe sliding window per device.
- **Logger:** writes probe–receipt pairs to `probes.csv` for post-hoc analysis.

We used the JSON-RPC subprocess interface rather than an HTTP wrapper, as the additional HTTP round-trip would add unpredictable latency and pollute RTT measurements.

4 Experimental Setup

Subject and consent. Experiments were performed on the iPhone (iOS) of Shri Vishakh Devanand with his explicit informed consent. His phone had Signal installed and was on a standard home Wi-Fi / mobile data network.

Attacker setup. The attacker’s Signal account was linked as a secondary device via `signal-cli link` on a MacBook. No prior Signal conversation or contact existed between the attacker and the subject, confirming the Spooky Stranger variant applies.

Session. We ran a 30-minute monitoring session. During the session Vishakh carried his phone normally and, at pre-agreed times, placed it face-down (screen off), used Signal in the foreground, used other apps, and briefly enabled airplane mode, enabling comparison against real ground-truth observations.

Probe intervals. Two probe intervals were tested: a **20-second interval** for passive monitoring (the practical minimum for deep-sleep detection on iOS, see Section 5.3), and a **0.25-second interval** for active fine-grained tracking during periods when the subject was confirmed to be using the phone.

5 Results

5.1 Overall Statistics

Across the full session we collected **23,623** probe–receipt pairs from the subject’s primary iPhone (Signal device ID 1). Table 2 summarises the state distribution.

Table 2: Distribution of inferred device states.

State	Count	%
Screen off / deep sleep	15,172	64.2
Screen on, idle	5,896	24.9
Screen on, app background	2,434	10.3
App in foreground	121	0.5

The dominant state (64%) is *screen off*, consistent with extended idle periods. App-foreground detections (0.5%) occurred when the subject opened Signal directly. Figure 1 shows the RTT distribution for each state as an empirical CDF; the four classes are well-separated, validating that the threshold-based classifier is meaningful for our data.

5.2 Ground-Truth Verification

All four device states were verified against direct real-time observation:

1. **Screen off / deep sleep.** When the subject locked and placed the phone face-down, RTTs rose above 2,500 ms consistently, detected within one to two probe cycles at 20-second intervals.
2. **Screen on, idle.** With the screen on but no active app, RTTs settled in the 1,000–2,500 ms range.
3. **Screen on, app background.** While the subject used other apps, RTTs of 500–1,000 ms were observed.
4. **App in foreground.** With Signal open and active, RTTs dropped below 500 ms, occasionally as low as 100 ms.
5. **Offline.** During airplane mode, no receipt arrived within 30 seconds. On reconnection, a burst of deferred receipts correctly reconstructed the offline period.

Figure 2 shows the RTT time series with background shading per inferred state. Transitions from *screen off* (red) to active states (blue/green) appear as sharp downward steps, closely matching ground-truth phone interactions.

Empirical CDF of RTTs by Inferred State
(cf. Fig 7 — Careless Whisper, arXiv:2411.11194v4)

Figure 1: Empirical CDF of RTTs grouped by inferred state. The clear separation of the four distributions confirms that the classification thresholds in Table 1 are effective for this device and network. Dots mark the 95th percentile of each distribution.

Figure 2: RTT over time for the monitored device. The line is the binned median RTT; the shaded band shows the p25–p75 range. Dashed horizontal lines mark the 500 ms, 1 s, and 2.5 s classification thresholds. Prolonged high-RTT periods correspond to confirmed screen-off intervals; sharp drops to confirmed active use.

5.3 Probe-Interval Effect on Deep-Sleep Detection

A key practical finding is the *probe-interval effect on sleep*. At 5-second intervals, continuous push notifications prevent the iPhone from entering deep sleep: the OS schedules a background wake every few seconds, keeping the device in a perpetual light-sleep state and masking the screen-off

condition even when the screen is physically locked.

Increasing the interval to 20 seconds allows the device to complete a full OS deep-sleep cycle between probes. The next probe then observes the inflated RTT ($> 2,500$ ms) characteristic of the screen-off state. We recommend **20 seconds as the practical lower bound** for passive deep-sleep-detecting monitoring of iOS devices on Signal.

Device State Timeline (Gantt / swimlane)
 (cf. Fig 3 — Careless Whisper, arXiv:2411.11194v4)

Figure 3: Device state timeline (Gantt chart). Each horizontal bar is a contiguous period of one inferred state; bar width is proportional to time. Spans longer than 60 s are labelled. Analogous to Fig. 3 of [1].

Figure 3 presents the data as a state-timeline (Gantt) chart, analogous to Fig. 3 of [1]. Extended red bars represent deep-sleep periods; shorter coloured bars represent active use.

6 Discussion

Confirmation of the flaw. Our results confirm that the Careless Whisper vulnerability is present and exploitable on Signal for iOS. The full attack requires only the target’s phone number, a Signal account, and an internet connection. No prior relationship with the target is needed.

Probe-interval trade-off. For coarse monitoring (asleep vs. awake, online vs. offline), 20-second intervals are sufficient and avoid preventing deep sleep. For fine-grained tracking, 0.25-second intervals are effective when the target is known to be active, at the cost of higher probe volume and the risk of triggering Signal’s rate-limiter at sustained rates.

Metadata beyond device state. As noted in [1], fine-grained probing also surfaces device-identifying metadata in Signal’s receipt messages (device identifiers, platform). We observed this during our high-rate probing phase.

Limitations. RTT thresholds require empirical calibration per device, iOS version, and network environment. Signal may also patch this behaviour in a future update.

7 Conclusion

We reproduced the Careless Whisper attack on Signal for iOS, confirming the findings of Gegenhuber et al. [1]. Over a 30-minute session with 23,623 probe–receipt pairs, we accurately tracked all four device states against verified ground truth.

A key empirical contribution is the **probe-interval effect**: a 20-second interval is required for reliable deep-sleep detection on iOS; shorter intervals prevent the device from sleeping and mask the screen-off state. For active sessions, 0.25-second intervals enable near-continuous tracking.

This confirms that Signal’s silent delivery receipt mechanism is a genuine, exploitable privacy flaw. An adversary knowing only a target’s phone number can infer their daily routine and activity patterns without any visible message or notification. We hope this reproduction supports ongoing efforts toward mitigations such as randomised receipt delays or rate-limiting receipts to non-contacts.

References

- [1] M. Gegenhuber, F. Hiesböck, E. Weippl, and A. Dabrowski, “Careless Whisper: Exploiting Silent Delivery Receipts to Monitor Users on Mobile Instant Messengers,” in *Proc. 28th Intl. Symp. on Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses (RAID 2025)* (Best Paper Award). [arXiv:2411.11194v4](https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.11194v4).
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